

PECULIARITIES OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN THE ONLINE SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article discusses the peculiarities of teaching Russian as a foreign language in the online system in Uzbekistan, the mandatory components of effective distance learning are identified: the content of education, the organization of education and the technical side of education. The author listed the network platforms popular among higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan, on the basis of which distance learning is carried out, noted the programs for video conferences that are popular among students and teachers.

Keywords: Russian as a foreign language, online learning system, efficiency, network platforms, features of teaching,

In the XXI century, there has been a steady trend towards a reorientation of the higher education system towards new values, where the humanization of the pedagogical process and the democratization of interpersonal relations began to be put at the forefront. Today, a higher education graduate must be competitive, in demand in the labor market, which a priori implies a high level of his general development, possession of information and communication competence, high professionalism, the ability to make independent decisions, non-standard thinking and productive adaptation to changing conditions. All this leads to the fact that at present pedagogical activity should be innovative, which is one of the essential factors for the successful educational activities of any educational institution. The reality is that it is innovation activity, on the one hand, that creates the basis for creating the competitiveness of an institution in the educational services market, and on the other hand, it determines the direction of professional growth of teaching staff, the creative search of each teacher, which really contributes to the personal growth of students.

In this regard, in recent years, the use of information technologies in the university has been increasingly expanding, which are not only modern technical means, but also new approaches to the learning process. This is due to the main goal of teaching foreign languages: the formation and development of the communicative culture of students, their practical mastery of a foreign language. The task of a university teacher is to create all the conditions for the practical mastery of the language by each student. This involves the choice of

such teaching methods that would allow him to show his activity and his creativity. This is the aim of modern innovative technologies associated with the use of various information technologies and Internet resources.

The peculiarities of teaching Russian as a foreign language are: a change in the learning environment of students, since work with a teacher in the classroom is transferred to the individual environment of each student, as well as changes in teaching methods in the classroom using textbooks and technical teaching aids. Online classes put before the teacher and students the conditions associated with the ability to work on the platforms ZOOM and Google MIT (Google Meet), knowledge of the features of the formation of the communicative competence of the language being studied in the new conditions, since the training takes place in the Internet environment using information technology and innovative teaching methods.

The teacher must have information competence to work on platforms and provide students with tasks that will have different forms of learning and take into account the motivation of students in the new online working environment. It is difficult to motivate students to learn a foreign language in new conditions, since each student learns in his own environment associated with the use of a computer, Internet connection, when it is not always possible to work online for technical reasons, when there is no Internet connection with a teacher, because a weak signal and the student becomes nervous and loses motivation to learn a foreign language (i.e. Russian).

The teacher, taking into account all these circumstances, should develop his own methodology for teaching Russian as a foreign language using innovative teaching methods, based on methodological knowledge and information and pedagogical teaching technologies, since traditional methods of working with a textbook in the classroom become little used and do not motivate students to work in the online system.

What can a Russian language teacher offer to students?! First of all, the widespread use of the Internet information and learning environment in conjunction with innovative teaching methods, since it contains sites of speakers of different languages and cultures, information from which can be used to teach types of speech activity, and the formation of students' communicative and intercultural competencies.

The language and information environment of the Internet makes it possible not only to motivate students to learn Russian as a foreign language online, but also to fulfill their needs: communicative - in communication,

cognitive - in search activities and gaming, associated with computer games and gaming methods for learning languages taken from Internet. In this regard, the use and improvement of the methods of the educational process and educational technologies is of particular importance. The use of a communicative approach to the study of Russian as a foreign language based on modern technologies is the norm of today. This is especially true for the sphere of studying Russian as a foreign language for students of universities in Uzbekistan, where interaction with a teacher in pairs cannot be effective without students independently mastering the necessary vocabulary, mastering the norms of the Russian literary language, as well as the ability to use language units in speech practice.

The main feature of the modern Russian as a foreign language lesson is the co-creation of the teacher and the student in cognition, in understanding linguistic phenomena. Live speech should constantly sound in pairs, and therefore ZOOM or Google Meet is relevant for distance learning using innovative teaching methods. Not the wording of the rules and exceptions to them, but the artistic texts and statements of the guys themselves. The task of the teacher is to find such language units in a work of art, after analyzing which, students will receive the key to unraveling the subtext, understanding the ideological and figurative content. Thus, in the process of studying Russian as a foreign language, the student must master stable skills of adequate perception and understanding of speech, as well as the ability to generate their own speech statement with certain communicative properties, and then it will be relevant to use ICT as one of the modern and innovative methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language for students in distance learning.

Thus, electronic genres of the Internet are becoming a source of learning content for modern students and a field of creative activity for a teacher. The teacher can take from the Internet types of audio texts for teaching listening and speaking, reading and writing, taking into account the level of language proficiency of the audience: weather forecast, news, sports reports, virtual tours of cities and museums, culinary recipes, theater posters, performances of talk shows on television channels. Thus, the learning environment is changing and the methods and forms of work with students are changing. Modern students need to present such content of education and forms of work that can evoke positive emotions in them when learning a language, interest them in the learning process itself online and speech activity on the Internet, teach them to empathize and emotionally perceive educational material, so that when learning to communicate in Russian as a foreign language they could express their

opinion on various topics and problems developed in the textbooks of Serafima Alekseevna Khavronina.

Thus, the teacher should offer students interactive and active forms of work related to individual and collective activities. For example, interactive forms of work are associated with the use of the project method, project wiki, discussion, web quests and gaming technologies in the classroom, which stimulates teamwork, which reflects the contribution of each project participant to joint activities at all stages of the project. Active forms of work are associated with the use of pedagogical technologies in teaching, such as excursion pedagogy, museum pedagogy, landscape and speech therapy technology. Active methods of work are aimed at performing creative, search, problem tasks, as they increase the creativity of students, enhance the individualization of learning, create an atmosphere of cooperation and thus support the motivation to study Russian as a foreign language.

Our observations indicate that the expansion of cognitive capabilities through the use of ICT in the study of Russian as a foreign language on the basis of the ZOOM and Google Meet platforms contributes to the development of a sustainable, conscious interest in learning new and immense. Stimulation is implemented in several ways: by irradiation - spreading interest in studying Russian as a foreign language based on innovative teaching methods, without leaving the computer - online, by being in demand in Internet lessons or when working independently with a computer of material from other disciplines, by involving students in educational and research work. The transfer of acquired knowledge, skills and abilities to non-educational activities deserves special attention, which is a sign of their interested development and demand. An equally important problem is the lack of motivation in learning the Russian language, and the teacher must constantly pay attention to the level of motivation of students, taking into account their modern interests and increase it by setting clear goals, diversifying the classroom using various innovative teaching methods on the ZOOM platform and Google Meet. Thus, there is no definite solution to all problems, and there are no precise instructions on how to deal with them. The best solution is to use a combination of different solutions, taking into account the characteristics of today's youth of the XXI century.

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